

Managing Work Place Motivation

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Abstract

This study focuses on the employee motivation among entrepreneur. Recent research the entrepreneurship have been largely focused on macro level environment forces. The development of entrepreneurial theory requires consideration of the motivation of people making entrepreneurial decision. We identify the major weakness that have limited the predictive power of previous research on this topic. We offer explicit solutions for the future research to adopt to overcome these problems.

Keywords: Emotion, Gender, Entrepreneurship.

Introduction

The term motivation has been derived from the word ‘motive’ which means drive, hence motivation is the derive to achieve target. Motive may be defined as an inner state of our mind that moves or energizes and directs our behavior towards our goals. Motives are expressions of a person’s goals or needs. In simple terms motives or needs are ways of behavior. They give direction to human behavior to achieve goals or fulfill needs.

Entrepreneurial motivation may be defined as a set of motives such as high need to achieve, moderate need for power and low affiliation motive which induce people to set up and run their own enterprises. A part from these entrepreneurs has other behavioral dimensions such as tolerance for ambiguity, problem solving, creativity etc. Motives are ways of behaviour. They give direction to human behavior to achieve goals or fulfill needs.

The common man thinks that people go into business and become entrepreneurs solely to make money. The desire to earn money is no doubt an important motivating force. But entrepreneurs are motivated not by profits alone. Several research studies have been conducted in India to identify the factors that inspire entrepreneurs.

Motivation is the process that motivates a person into action and induces him to continue the course of action for the achievement of goals. It is an ongoing process because human needs /goals are never completely satisfied. Motivation may be defined as one’s willingness to exert high level of efforts towards the accomplishment of goal or fulfillment of need.

The entrepreneurial motivation may be defined as the process that activates and motivates the entrepreneur to exert higher level of efforts for the achievement of his/her entrepreneurial goals.

Motivation

“Motivation is the reported urge or tension to move in a given direction or to achieve a certain goal”

Characteristics of Motivation

- Motivation is always total and not piece meal:
- It means that a person cannot be motivated if some of needs are partly satisfied
- Motivation may be financial or non-financial:
 1. Financial Incentives are the monetary benefits provided to an employee in the form of higher pay, bonus, commission etc.
 2. Non –financial incentives are the non-monetary benefits such as greater decision authority and so on.
- Methods of motivation may be positive as well as negative:
- Many people think that the method of motivation should always positive. It may even be negative.
- Motivation is a psychological concept:
- A subordinate whose need have been fully satisfied, feels mentally relieved. E.g. Mental satisfaction
- Motivation is a continuous process:
 1. Human needs are infinite. This process is unending one

Types of Motivation

1. Financial Motivation

It involves money payments by the employer –either directly or indirectly. Higher wages and salaries, bonus, commission etc.

2. Non-financial Motivation

It does not involves money payment. These are also important in motivating employees. They are:

- Job security
- Challenges work
- Recognition
- Better designation
- Opportunities for advancement

3. Extrinsic Motivation

It is available only after the completion of particular job. For examples Increase in health insurance; Increase in benefits; Additional rest periods or holidays.

4. Intrinsic Motivation

It is opposite to extrinsic motivation. This type of motivation is available at the time of the performance of the work itself.eg, Increasing in power; Delegation of authority and responsibility

5. Negative Motivation

It is based on force of fear. If the worker fails to complete the work, They may be threatened with demotion, dismissed, lay-off, pay-cut etc. It gives maximum benefits in short-run. In the long-run, there are no such benefits available to the organization. This type of motivation causes angry and frustration.

6. Positive Motivation

It is based on rewards, praise. The workers are offered incentives for achieving desired goals. They incentive may be the shape of more pay, promotion recognition of work etc.

Factors Motivate the Entrepreneur to Establish an Enterprise

Several research studies have been carried out to identify the factors that motivate to people to start business enterprises. some of the factors;

Motive for astarting an enterprises:

1. Internal Factors
2. External Factors
3. Ambitions Factors
4. Compelling Factors
5. Facilitating Factors

Internal Factors

1. Educational background
2. Family back ground
3. Desire to be free and independent
4. Desire to do something innovative

External Factors

1. Assistance from government
2. Machinery on hire purchase
3. Heavy demand for product
4. Encouragement from big business units.

Ambitions Factors

1. To make money
2. To continue family business
3. To gain social prestige
4. To fulfill desire of self/wife/parents
5. To fulfill desire of wife/parents/self

Compelling Factors

1. Unemployment.
2. Make use of idle funds.
3. Dissatisfaction with the job so far held or occupation pursued.
4. Make use of technical /professional skills

Facilitating Factors

1. Success stories of entrepreneurs
2. Property inherited
3. Advice or influences of family members /relatives / friends
4. Previous association (experience in the same or other line of activity)

Conclusion

People are capable of remarkable achievement if they are provided with the right environment and given the right motivation leadership. When you motivate, you increase morale and in return you increase productivity.

Motivation is the process in which behavior is initiated, guided and maintains goal oriented behavior. Motivation cannot be directly observed but through behavior we see it manifested. It is though as the driving force that compels person to do something.

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